

Experimental evaluation of the plane stress fracture toughness for ultra-fine grained Al/Al specimens prepared by accumulative roll bonding process

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Abstract

In this research, the plane stress fracture toughness of ultra-fine grained Al/Al specimens produced through accumulative roll bonding (ARB) process was investigated for the first time. Specimens were produced successfully by ARB process up to 7 cycles with the amount of 50% thickness reduction in each cycle at the room temperature and without the use of lubricant. The fracture toughness was evaluated for the annealed, and different ARB cycles using ASTM E561 standard and compact tension specimens. Also, mechanical properties, tensile fracture surfaces and crystallite size of ultra-fine grained Al/Al ARBed specimens were evaluated by uniaxial tensile tests, microhardness measurements, scanning electron microscopy and X-ray diffraction. By increasing the number of ARB cycles, fracture toughness was increased and the maximum value of this parameter achieved at the last cycle which was about $25.4 \text{ MPam}^{1/2}$ that it was increased to 155% higher than the annealed specimen. Results of X-ray diffraction demonstrated that by increasing the number of ARB cycles, crystallite size decreased and from 1341nm for annealed samples reached to 175nm for 7th cycle ARBed specimen. Also, by increasing the number of ARB cycles up to the 7th cycle, tensile strength and microhardness of ultra-fine grained Al/Al samples increased to 232MPa and 51VHN, respectively. At first, the value of elongation decreased and then increased. Results of SEM showed that ductile fracture mode with large dimples happened in

the annealed specimen, changed to shear ductile fracture with elongated spherulitic shear and fine dimples after ARB process.

Keywords: Fracture toughness; ARB process; Ultra-fine grained Al/Al sheet; Mechanical properties; SEM.

1. Introduction

In the last decade, aluminum as a desirable material has absorbed interest of many researchers for various applications such as industries, automobile manufacturing and aerospace [1-4]. In other hands during these years, bulk nano and ultrafine-grained (UFG) materials have attracted significant research interest, because it reveals high strength besides good ductility and toughness, desirable corrosion resistance and high-speed superplastic deformation [5-8]. Various procedures can be used to produce nano and UFG materials. Top-down and bottom-up methods are the important and main classification of manufacturing nano and UFG materials [9, 10]. The bottom-up technology included many fabrication methods. For example, vapor deposition mechanical alloying and rapid solidification are placed in the bottom-up procedures. Also on the other side, the most important and usable method from top-down procedures is severe plastic deformation (SPD) process. So far, different accepted and successful SPD methods were introduced that fabricating various metals such as equal channel angular pressing (ECAP) [11-13] and rolling (ECAR) [14, 15], high pressure torsion (HPT) [11, 16-18], extrusion compression (CEC) [19, 20], multi axial forging (MAF) [21], constrained groove pressing (CGP) [22], cyclic, and accumulative roll bonding (ARB) [23, 24]. The common feature of all SPD methods is that the dimensions of specimens after and before applied procedure are the same and constant [9]. Between SPD

methods, accumulative roll bonding has some better characteristics, for example, ARB without a need to expensive equipment with high power capacity can be applied for different materials [9]. Also, ARB has industrial potential because of high production rate and continuous production procedure [5, 23, 24]. The accumulative roll bonding is a repeatable technology of preparing, surface treatment, stacking and rolling sheets with similar dimensions for a various number of ARB cycles in order to obtain desirable mechanical properties that are constrained by limitation such as the growth of edge cracks [23, 25, 26]. This process can be performed for a wide range of metals. In recent years the accumulative roll bonding process has been broadly utilized for fabrication in form of sheets and foils and for various materials such as pure aluminum [6, 24-26], aluminum alloys [4, 10, 23, 27], Zr [28], Cu[29-31], Brass[32], Ti [33, 34], Mg [35, 36], and IF steel sheets [37-39]. The conclusions of the all of these works mainly proved that the ARB process is also able in manufacturing of the multilayered from same or different materials [40-42] and composites with metal matrix [5, 43-47] with desirable and improved mechanical properties, microstructure and also conclusions of some studies demonstrated that the mechanical properties such as tensile strength and microhardness can be increased more than two and even more than three times from the amounts of primary material before ARB process, but the elongation decreased.

Nano-structured materials particularly ARB process, may not be utilized in engineering structures and appliances unless a detailed understanding of their fracture properties is provided. There are some works in the fracture behavior of UFG materials that some of these studies reported fracture toughness reduction and increase after grain refinement. It is reported that UFG nickel produced by high-pressure torsion process (HPT) and commercially pure titanium prepared by equal channel angular pressing (ECAP) after one pass, has lower fracture toughness compared to initial samples

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[48, 49] also, it is reported that UFG pure Cu (CGP) and Al 7075 (ECAP) has higher fracture toughness compared to initial samples [50, 51]. But so far no research has been done for material that produced by ARB process. In this research and for the first time, the effect of ARB process on the plane stress fracture toughness, mechanical properties and crystallite size of Al 1050 were evaluated through experimental procedures. ARB process was applied at seven passes at room temperature. The mechanical properties, fracture properties, and microstructures of initial and processed samples were experimentally investigated by uniaxial tensile test, microhardness, fractography, fracture toughness and XRD.

2. Experimental Procedure

2.1. Research material

The chemical composition and specifications of the unprocessed material (commercial pure aluminum in the form of sheets with initial same thickness of 1 mm) are given in table 1. Before ARB process, due to the achieve well-structure, samples were annealed. Annealing and cooling were done in the furnace at 380°C for 60 min and in the air at ambient temperature, respectively.

2.2. Accumulative Roll Bonding Process

In the present research and in order to evaluate the tensile fracture surfaces, mechanical properties and plane stress fracture toughness of multilayer Al-Al manufactured through ARB process, sheets were prepared into 120 mm × 75 mm × 1 mm in length, width, and thickness, respectively. Images in Fig.1 illustrate the basic of the ARB process utilized for the manufacturing of multilayer Al-Al

in this investigation. The surface preparation was performed in the multi-steps such as degreasing by acetone, drying in air, roughening by circular stainless steel wire brush with dimensions of 8 mm and 0.3 mm in diameter and wire thickness, respectively. Then after surface preparation, the two aluminum sheets were stack on each other and in order to avoid sliding, the stack was fastened by steel wires at four corner points for ARB process, and roll bonded by 50% reduction in thickness. Then, the roll bonded sheets were cut in half and this method was repeated to seven cycles at ambient temperature and without using lubricant. Rolling of the stacked samples by using a laboratory rolling mill with a capacity of 20 tons and a 107 mm diameter roll mill at a rolling speed of 14 rpm. Also to diminish reformation of oxide layers on the surface, tried to reduce the time between surface preparations and rolling.

2.3. Structural evaluation

In order to evaluate qualitatively and quantitatively for different ARB cycles, XRD measurements were carried out on the RD–TD plane of the ARB processed sheets. The XRD experiments were performed by an X-ray diffractometer (XRD, Bruker Advance D8) using Cu $k\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda=0.1542$ nm). The X-ray was operated at 40 kV, 0.5 Step Size and 40 mA and the data was collected at room temperature with a 2θ range between 30 and 80. The Williamson–Hall formula and X'Pert High Score software were used to analyze the XRD data. Also the crystallite size were calculated for each peak, separately and then the average of crystallite size for each peak at the different ARB pass reported.

2.4. Mechanical properties

Mechanical properties of ultra-fine grain Al/Al fabricated by the ARB process were studied through uniaxial tensile tests and microhardness measurements. The uniaxial tensile test specimens were prepared for the annealed and ARB processed sheets oriented along the rolling direction according to the ASTM: E8M standard. The gauge length and width of the tensile test specimens were 25 and 6 mm, respectively. The uniaxial tensile tests were performed at a nominal initial strain rate of $1.6 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at room temperature using SANTAM tensile testing machine. The Vickers microhardness tests were done for annealed, and ARBed specimen using JENUS apparatus under a load of 200 gr applied for 10 s. Microhardness tests had been implemented to the aluminum layers at ten different points randomly on the cross-sections perpendicular to the rolling direction. Then, for each aluminum layers the minimum and maximum hardness were disregarded.

2.5. Plane stress fracture toughness

In order to assess fracture properties of ARBed samples, the specimens of different ARB cycles (first, third, fifth and seventh pass) and annealed sample were prepared. Fracture test were done on at least three samples for each pass to investigate the repeatability of the results. Standard Compact tension C(T) sample introduced by ASTM-E647 standard was used. According to ASTM-E647 standard CT samples were prepared by wire cut machine. Pre-cracks are made in the specimen through wire-cutting technique. This pre-crack creation approach was approved by Mourad [52]. The specimen size was 23.75 mm×22.8 mm×1 mm thick which is shown in Fig. 2. In the specimen a narrow slit was introduced by machining. It was terminated into a 60° v-notch.

The tip of the v-notch was further extended up to 1 mm with $\left(\frac{a_0}{w}\right)$ ratio equal to 0.40. This extension was done through wire-cut machining with the wire radius of 200 μm . It is to be noted that the CT type specimen is under purely Mode I loading condition. All of fracture tests are performed by displacement control at a constant rate. The experimental set-up of CT specimens is shown in Fig. 3. Specimens were loaded quasi-statically at a moving head speed of 0.05 mm/s up to the maximum load and beyond, until the full separation of the specimen.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Structural evaluation

Fig. 4 demonstrated the typical XRD patterns of pure Al and Al/Al with the index plane after different ARB cycles. The crystallite size, as one of the important structural parameters of nano-materials, can be obtained by X-ray diffraction (XRD) technique, as the crystallite size is related to the diffraction peak broadening. Significant peak broadening is observed especially for the smallest crystallite size values. It can be seen that by increasing the applied strain, much change in peak location have not being seen and also by increasing the ARB cycles the peak broad increased.

Fig. 5 illustrates the variation of crystallite size at various ARB passes and pure Al. the crystallite size from 1341nm for pure Al reach to about 175nm at the seven pass. In general we can say that the microstructure variation is based on the separation of grains. Can be said about ultra-grained fined at the ARBed samples that in the ARB process due to high applied strain by increasing the number of ARB cycle, the boundaries of different geometry are arranged in parallel bundles and according to the axis of the deformation find the determined direct. By increasing the stress and

strain, the number and failure to comply minor borders and the boundaries of different geometry are increased and the distance between them decreased and finally this mechanism would be latest fine-grained [53].

3.1. Fractography

Tensile rupture surfaces after uniaxial tensile test were investigated by scanning electron microscopy for evaluation the fracture mode. Tensile fracture surfaces of primary strips and the multilayers Al/Al as a function of the ARB passes are presented in Figs. 6 and 7, respectively. According to Fig. 6 for initial strips, were viewed that the common ductile fracture mechanism accompanied by deep equiaxed or hemispheroidal dimples in the rupture surfaces of the initial annealed sheet. Also noted that in the most materials have a FCC crystal structure existence ductile tensile fractures by equiaxed or hemispheroidal dimples [54-56]. This type of rupture happens by microvoids formation and coalescence, crack growth and finally shear fracture at an angle relative to the tensile direction [54, 56].

According to Fig. 7, by increasing ARB cycles, lamellar structure diminished but it can be seen after final cycle (seventh cycle). Also observed that by increasing the ARB cycles dimples are smaller and shallower compared to annealed sample. The appearance of these dimples in the rupture surfaces of the ARBed samples (Fig. 7) suggests happening of the common shear ductile fracture mechanism that is similar to the initial sample but the dimples are smaller and shallower that causes the increasing tensile strength and decreasing elongation compared to the initial sample [54, 57]. The failure surface of the initial (Fig. 6) and ARBed samples (Fig. 7) shows some hemispheroidal and small dimples that some dimples are distributed in one or other directions

because of applying unequal triaxial stresses. These existences are the specifications of a typical ductile fracture. Each dimple attributed to a crack nucleation site, which has been linked up during plastic deformation process [58]. Briefly we can say that for initial strips, were observed the ductile fracture accompanied by deep and equiaxed dimples So that high deformation and necking in the macro state and for Aluminum-Aluminum sheet after ARB process, ductile fracture accompanied by dimpled samples and shear zones were observed. As well as dimples size of Al/Al ARBed its smaller and shallower than dimples of initial strips.

3.2. Mechanical properties

The annealed material (AA1050) has the low yield tensile strength, and very large elongation about 34% and tensile strength of nearly 55MPa are obtained. The stress–strain curves of the multilayers Al/Al as a function of the ARB cycles are presented in Fig. 8. According to Fig.9, ultimate and yield tensile strength is quickly enhanced after the first cycle of the ARB process and then by rising ARB passes up to 7-pass, it slowly increased. The strain hardening rate of the soft phase and flow properties of the constituent phases has effects on the mechanical properties of the metallic multilayer specially tensile properties [59, 60]. Two basic mechanisms are responsible for strengthening during ARB process such as strain hardening by dislocations and grain refinement [26, 59, 61, 62]. Increasing the value of strength in the initial cycles (at least before 3) of the ARB process, attributed by strain hardening and cold work as an important role. [62, 63]. After the initial cycles (after third pass) and by decreasing the effect of work hardening, strengthening and higher strengths are achieved by gradual evolution of microstructure and grain refinement [24, 33, 63, 64]. The bond strength between aluminum layers increased with rising the number of the ARB

cycles and lead to the increase of the strength. The maximum yield and tensile strength achieved 198MPa and 231.7MPa at the 7th cycle, respectively.

The values of yield strength (YS), ultimate tensile strength (UTS) and elongation achieved from the engineering stress–strain curves (Fig. 8) for the Al/Al ARBed specimens at different cycles and annealed samples are presented in Fig. 9. According to Fig. 9 the elongation of phases indicates a sharp decreasing in the first ARB cycle and then the elongation is improved by continuing the ARB process. The low elongations value in the ARBed specimens can be attributed to the high strain hardening and weak bond between aluminum layers. Increasing the elongation after the 1th cycle, can be due to the grain refinement, decreasing effect of the strain hardening and bond strength between aluminum layers. Elongation of multilayered Al/Al after the 1th cycle of ARB was 3.44% and improved as ARB process continued and arrived an amount of 7.82% after the 7th cycle (last pass).

Fig10. Shows the Vickers micro hardness variations of Al/Al during different cycles of the ARB process. It proved that by rising the number of ARB cycles, the microhardness of Al/Al increased. The micro hardness of phases indicates a sharp rise in the 1th ARB cycle from 25 to 45 VHN. After the 1th cycle, there is a moderate increase in the microhardness, and finally it approximately gets constant in the last cycle (7th) of the ARB process and reached on amount value of 51.5 VHN after 7th cycle. The increasing rate of micro hardness in the initial cycles of ARB is attributed to the high rate of strain hardening [59, 65] and in the next cycles both of strain hardening and grain refinement are effective on the micro hardness increase until in the last ARB cycles, the micro hardness reaches an approximately constant value because the materials have arrived a steady-state density of dislocation and consequently. Annihilation in the dynamic recovery process and

dynamic balance between dislocation generation during plastic deformation causes of the created steady-state density of dislocations [59, 63].

3.3. Plane stress fracture toughness

Fig. 11 shows the load-CMOD (Crack Mouth Opening Displacement) curves for the annealed and ultra-fine grain ARBed specimens at the different ARB cycles. According to Fig. 11 maximum load of the specimens (P_{max}) can be achieved. As expected, because of the high reduction of ductility after ARB process, a linear relationship has been achieved between the load and CMOD for the ARBed specimens. By increasing the number of ARB cycles, the value of P_{max} enhanced and maximum value obtained at the last cycle.

According to ASTM E-561, the plane stress fracture toughness of the specimens (K_C), can be obtained. It should be noted that, the value of K_C for different ARB cycles must be determined at the instability condition from the tangency between the R-curve and the applied K-curve of the specimens. In addition, using ASTM: E8M, for the CT specimens, the crack grows resistance (K_R), can be calculated as follows:

$$k_{r_i} = \frac{p_i}{b\sqrt{w}} \times f_i \left(\frac{a}{w} \right) \quad (1)$$

$$f_i \left(\frac{a}{w} \right) = \left[\frac{2 + \frac{a}{w}}{\left(1 - \frac{a}{w}\right)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \right] \left[0.886 + 4.64 \left(\frac{a}{w} \right) - 13.32 \left(\frac{a}{w} \right)^2 + 14.72 \left(\frac{a}{w} \right)^3 - 5.6 \left(\frac{a}{w} \right)^4 \right] \quad (2)$$

Where, (P_{max}), (w), (B) and (a) are the maximum applied load, sample width (19mm), sample thickness (1mm) and the crack size (7.6mm), respectively and it is valid for $\frac{a_0}{w} \geq 0.35$. The

coefficient $f_i \left(\frac{a}{w} \right)$, which only depends on the specimen geometry and based on the standard, the given expression for $f_i \left(\frac{a}{w} \right)$ is considered. Fig. 12 demonstrates the step of crack growth for the 7th cycle of ARB process specimen during fracture test. It is seen that the crack grows straightly in the direction of crack front for all specimens which is an evidence for symmetry and pure opening mode loading condition. Plane stress fracture toughness of each cycle is calculated using Eq (1). Considering the material and geometry conditions, the calculated Pmax and fracture toughness are within the valid range indicated by the standard. Fig. 13 shows the R-curved for annealed, 1th, 3th, 5th and 7th cycle of the ARB process. Fig. 14 shows the fracture toughness of annealed and ARBed specimens at the different ARB cycles. The percentage changes in this figure have been seen compared to the fracture toughness of annealed specimens. According to these results, the fracture toughness increases after the 1th ARB cycle from 9.9 to 16.1 MPa.m^{1/2}. This is due to the increase in strength of annealed sample after the 1th ARB cycle. For the next ARB cycles, fracture toughness increases again so that after 7th cycle, it is 155% higher than that of annealed specimen. Since important and influencing parameters on the value of fracture toughness of metallic materials are strength and ductility. It can be said that for the first cycles (first and third pass), strength increasing is overcoming compared to the ductility reduction. As mentioned in our results and in the similar investigations, after a remarkable reduction in ductility of material for the first ARB cycles, the ductility increased with very low rate. So one reason for increasing the value of fracture toughness enhancement in ARBed samples after first cycles (first and third pass) is because of the values of strength and ductility are enhanced in compared with annealed samples, although the increase rate of the strength is higher than ductility. Also the trend of increases in the fracture toughness is similar to strength so that after first pass increased sharply and then with low

rate improved. This trend for Cu CGPed samples also occurred [50] but for ECAPed samples the value of fracture toughness decreased after first cycle and then increased [48, 49, 51].

In the other hand and from 3th to 7th cycle, both values of elongation and tensile strength increased, continuously, that is due to the grained refinement, because the grained refinement is the only mechanism that enhances strength and ductility at the same time. According to fig.5 by increasing the number of ARB cycles, crystallite size decreased and the crystallite size at the last cycle reach to 175nm that can be said after 3th cycle, the effect of cold work decreased and grain refinement can improved the value of plane stress fracture toughness at the mid and last cycles. In the UFG materials due to the higher grain boundaries volume fraction, crack tip blunting and crack arrest play much more important role in fracture resistance which results in fracture toughness enhancement [51]. Furthermore, as the grain size decreases, some mechanisms such as grain boundary accommodation, grain boundary triple junction activity, grain nucleation and grain rotation are intensified [51]. Since these control rate mechanisms of the plastic energy release at the nanoscale, it is expected that fracture toughness increases after grain refinement [66]. Some experimental works on metallic materials proved that the hardening region such as plastic zone is enlarged after grain refinement [67-69]. This fact can be also assumed as one of the reasons for fracture resistance enhancement observed in UFG materials.

4. Conclusions

In the present investigation, ultra-fine grain Al/Al was prepared by ARB process. Mechanical properties, fracture toughness, tensile fracture surfaces and crystallite size for ARBed specimens at different cycles of ARB process leads to the following results:

- I. For the first time, plane stress fracture toughness of ultra-fine grain Al/Al produced by ARB process were evaluated that favorable results were obtained for this process. By increasing the number of ARB cycles, value of fracture toughness increased so that maximum value obtained at the last cycle and compared annealed sample improved to 155%.
- II. The crystallite size, as one of the important structural parameters of nano-materials, were obtained by X-ray diffraction. By increasing the number of ARB cycles, crystallite size decreased and from 1341nm for annealed specimens reach to 175nm for 7th cycle.
- III. Yield and tensile strength were quickly enhanced after the 1th pass of the ARB process and then by increasing ARB cycles up to 7-cycles, it slowly enhanced and the maximum yield and tensile strength arrived 198MPa and 231.7MPa at the 7th cycle, respectively.
- IV. Result of microhardness measurement indicated that the sharp rising in the 1th cycle and value of microhardness enhanced from 25 to 45 VHN. After the 1th cycle, there was a moderate increase and finally, the microhardness reaches an approximately constant value.
- V. Observations of SEM showed that the fracture mode in the accumulatively roll bonded AA1050 sheet was the shear ductile rupture with elongated spherulitic shear dimples.

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Appendix I: Notation

SPD	Severe Plastic Deformation
UFG	Ultra-Fine Grain
ARB	Accumulative Roll bonding
ECAP	Equal Channel Angular Pressing
ECAR	Equal Channel Angular Rolling
HPT	High Pressure Torsion
CEC	Cyclic Extrusion Compression
MAF	Multi Axial Forging
CGP	Constrained Groove Pressing
K _c	plane stress fracture toughness
KR	crack grows resistance
CT	Compact tension
P _{max}	the maximum applied load
B	Thickness
w	Width
a	Crack size
$\frac{a_0}{w}$	crack length to specimen width ratio
CMOD	crack mouth opening displacement

Tables

Table 1: Specifications of commercial purity aluminum.

Material	Chemical Composition (wt. %)	Yield Strength (MPa)	Tensile Strength (MPa)	Elongation (%)	Hardness (HVN)
Al 1050_Anealed	99.44 Al, 0.406 Fe, 0.121 Si, 0.033	39	61	35	25

Table 2: Variations in the mechanical properties, plane stress fracture toughness and crystallite size for annealed and ARBed specimens

Number of ARB cycles	UTS (MPa)	Elongation (%)	K_c (MPa.m ^{1/2})	Microhardness (VHN)	Crystallite size (nm)
Anneal	61.3	34	9.9	25	1341
1 th cycle	153	3.5	16.1	45	621
3 th cycle	185.5	5.3	22.7	48	264
5 th cycle	209.1	7.1	24	49.7	231
7 th cycle	231	7.8	25.4	51.5	174

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